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The Unraveled Stories of Bangsamoro Learners in English Language Learning

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Abstract

The main thrust of this study was to explore the English language learning experiences of five Grade 6 Bangsamoro honor pupils at Mapayag Elementary School during the 2022-2023 academic year, employing a phenomenological research design. It uncovered that learners acquire English through various channels including parental assistance, media exposure, and peer interactions at home, while relying on personal efforts, teacher guidance, and peer engagement at school. In the community, learning occurs through interactions with playmates, friends, and relatives. However, learners encounter barriers such as embarrassment, mockery, and limited parental education. The findings underscored the challenges faced by Bangsamoro learners in English language usage due to constrained opportunities and social pressures. The study concluded by recommending initiatives to increase English usage across different contexts, foster interactions with English speakers, expand vocabulary, and emphasize correct language usage to enhance learners' confidence.

Keywords: *English language learning, Bangsamoro learners, home, school, community*

Introduction

Language is a way of communicating thoughts and feelings through signs and symbols. The information is encoded and decoded using these signs and symbols. There are numerous languages used throughout the world. The mother tongue is the first language that a baby learns. It is the language that the person has grown up hearing. A second language is any additional language that is learnt or acquired. The deliberate process of learning a language other than one's first language (L1) is known as second language acquisition. The process must begin after the first languages have already been learned, as bilingualism and multilingualism are frequently mistaken.

After mastering one's home tongue, learning a second or foreign language is not a simple task. It requires more work to learn, making it a challenging challenge for Bangsamoro kids. Students from Bangsamoro face numerous difficulties while they learn English. In Muslim Mindanao's Bangsamoro Autonomous Region, English is taught as a foreign language. From first grade through the bachelor's level, it is a national requirement. Regardless of their socioeconomic situation, linguistic heritage, or cultural or background, all children are required to learn English. Students from Bangsamoro are also not an exception.

In the Philippines, the English language learning setting is a mixture of students with various ethnicities and of different horizon, for instance the Bangsamoro Autonomous Region in Muslim Mindanao. The community is populated with diverse ethnicity such as Meranao, Maguindanaon, Iranon, Teduray and other ethnic groups with unique dialects, where in school, students are being taught that English is an international language and be proficient in terms of grammar, pronunciation, vocabulary, comprehension, and fluency as the parameters of English language proficiency. However, it has been a challenge for language teachers to have the full commitment of the students to speak the language fluently and to get the students' maximum participation during learning instruction.

The process of learning a second language is thus influenced by a wide range of elements, including attitude, self-confidence, motivation, length of exposure, classroom settings, environment, family background, and the availability of qualified teachers (Verghese, 2009). Here, the authors undertook a study to examine the many causes of the difficulties encountered by second-language learners. The three factors were environment, attitude, and instructor skill.

Furthermore, the success of the learning process is greatly influenced by the environment and family background. Another affective aspect in learning a second language is attitude. The way you feel and think about something is your attitude. According to Narayanan et al. (2008), learners' perceptions about the target language and its speakers, the learning scenario, and the language learning environment all appear to have a role in how successfully they pick up a second language. The competence of the teacher is a variable aspect that influences the acquisition of a second language, much like the surroundings and attitude. He should be fluent in the language and have a good understanding of and experience with effective language teaching strategies (Verghese, 2009).

The many methods and circumstances from the social backdrop on their environment have an impact on Bangsamoro language learners as they study English. Their experiences, learning styles, and impediments to acquiring the English language vary. They learn to utilize the language more as a result of increased exposure.

Because most residents of the Bangsamoro Autonomous Region in Muslim Mindanao (BARMM) do not speak English at home, it has been observed that the Bangsamoro community finds it challenging to acquire the language. Even in the classroom, the majority of the teachers speak Filipino or their native tongue. Additionally, the majority of residents of the community are Maguindanaon. The local population does not speak English. Similar difficulties and difficulties were encountered by students when teaching elementary-level language to the Bangsamoro population. Additionally, pronunciation and linguistic structure were challenges for learners.

The students at Mapayag Elementary School are all Bangsamoro who came from various rural communities, especially the seven

barangays of the Datu Anggal Midtimbang municipality in Maguindanao del Sur, which is part of Bangsamoro Autonomous Region in Muslim Mindanao. The researcher of this study is also a Bangsamoro and has been a regular teacher and member of the faculty at this school since 2018 together with the bulk of the professors and staff.

In this regard, the researcher as an educator would like to investigate the unraveled stories of the Bangsamoro learners in English Language Learning specifically on how do they learn English language at home, school and in the community and would like also to investigate the barriers of their English language learning in the said social context

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the unraveled stories of the grade 6 honor Bangsamoro learners in English Language Learning in Mapayag Elementary School during the school year 2022-2023. Specifically, this study attempted to answer the following questions:

1. How do learners learn English in the following social contexts:
 - 1.1. home;
 - 1.2. school; and
 - 1.3. community?
2. What are the barriers in English Language learning in following social contexts:
 - 2.1. home;
 - 2.2. school; and
 - 2.3. community?
3. Based on the findings, what theory in English Language Learning can be generated?

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed a descriptive qualitative research design to delve into the English language learning experiences of Bangsamoro learners. Specifically, it aimed to uncover their methods of acquiring English and identify the obstacles they face in learning the language within the contexts of home, school, and the community.

Participants

The study collected the information from five Grade 6 Section A honor pupils at Mapayag Elementary School during the academic year 2022-2023. These pupils were purposively selected as respondents due to their proficiency in the English language.

Instruments

This study utilized a semi-structured interview guide questionnaire administered to five honor pupils from Grade 6A of Mapayag Elementary School during the academic year 2022-2023. The instrument underwent verification and review by language experts. It comprised open-ended questions divided into two parts, aimed at eliciting information about the English language learning experiences of Bangsamoro learners. The first part focused on how these learners acquire English at home, school, and in the community, with the intention of sharing insights to aid other learners facing similar challenges. The second part explored the barriers encountered by learners in English language acquisition across these three contexts.

Each interview began with an acclimatization phase to ensure the participant's psychological and emotional readiness. Questions were initially framed in English, with ready translations available in Filipino to facilitate understanding, considering the participants' proficiency in the Filipino language. This approach aimed to ensure clarity and obtain comprehensive responses. The semi-structured format aimed to guide the interview process while avoiding leading questions, as recommended by Morse and Richards (2002) cited in Kalis (2018).

Procedure

The study followed a detailed procedure, starting with sending a transmittal letter to the Principal of Mapayag Elementary School to seek approval for the study. The same letter was sent to the class adviser of Grade 6A to discuss the study's objectives. Additionally, a letter of consent was sent to the guardians of the participants to seek permission and inform them about the study.

Upon receiving approval, the researcher scheduled in-depth interviews with the participants. Since the participants lived far from the researcher's location, they were invited to the researcher's place for the interviews, conducted at their most convenient time. The in-depth interviews, lasting approximately one hour, were conducted with the participants at the researcher's place, with the consent of their guardians. Interview instruments and materials were prepared, and the interviews were conducted in the Maguindanaon language.

After the interviews, the researcher carefully transcribed the data, ensuring the accuracy and clarity of the information provided by the participants. Transcribed data were reviewed multiple times against the participants' written answers to ensure accuracy.

Ethical Considerations

The researcher thoroughly addressed ethical considerations before conducting the study. Necessary measures were taken to uphold the rights of the participants, including respect for privacy and protection from physical and psychological harm. Transmittal letters sent to the principal, participants' class adviser, and parents/guardians explicitly stated the agreement between both parties the researcher and the participants to engage in the interview process.

Participants were informed in advance that all gathered information would only be accessed by the researcher and the adviser. Additionally, a confidentiality clause was upheld, ensuring that identifying details, such as names, would not be included in transcripts or the final report, thus respecting the dignity of the subjects. For added confidentiality and safety, voice recordings were deleted after transcription, further safeguarding the participants' privacy.

Lastly, participants were provided with clear and sufficient background information about the study to enable them to make informed decisions regarding their participation. This ensured that participants understood the purpose and scope of the study before consenting to take part.

Results and Discussion

The Learners Learn English Language at Home

The following table shows the results of the study taken from the in-depth interviews. The formulated meanings, codes, and themes of the significant statements about English Language learning at home is shown in table 1.1.

Table 1.1. *Learner's English Language Learning at Home*

Participant	Significant Statement	Formulated Meaning	Emergent Theme	Code
1	My mother taught me gradually in English Language for me to learn it.	Mother's support is a cause of learning of the child at home.	mother assistance to learn English	001
2	My mother makes me to watch English cartoon movies in television and makes me to read English reading materials and I used to ask the meaning of every unfamiliar English language word to my mother.	Mother's strategies/ways in learning English language through watching of Television and English reading materials.	Mother's assistance to learn English	001
			Watching of Television	002
			Reading of English materials.	003
			Expanding Vocabulary	004
3	My Father taught me in English Language.	Father support is a cause learning of child at home.	Father's assistance to learn English	005
4	My father and my mother they are both teaching me in English Language and when I'm watching television and I encountered unfamiliar words I ask them on their meaning.	Supports of both parents are the cause learning of child at home and watching of television.	Parent's assistance to learn	006
			English, Watching of Television, Expanding Vocabulary	002
				004
5	My mother and my father are both teaching me in English Language.	Supports of both parents are the cause learning of child at home.	Parent's assistance to learn English	006

Table 1.1 Presents English Language learning at Home. Majority participants agreed that they learned English at home because of the help/supports of their mother or father and sometimes with the help of both parents and some of them are learning English Language by watching of television, reading of English materials, and expanding of vocabulary during these events.

Mother assistant to learn English. A mother can help her child in learning English Language at home. Participant 1 coded 001 learned English Language with her mother's assistant to learn English and she said "*Pinamanduan ako ni umie sa English uway na peropro bu para pegkataw ako*" My mother taught me gradually in English Language for me to learn it. She affirmed that she learned English Language with her mother assistant. This implies that her mother is having enough knowledge in English Language to make her learn English at home.

Watching television. The gadget can be a source of learning in English Language at home. A learner can be expose in the said language by tuning it in its English programs which enhance her/his knowledge in this language.

Reading of English Materials. It is a traditional way of learning. It gave a learner a lot of knowledge, information and more discoveries. The more the learner read English materials the more they enhance their learning in English.

Expanding vocabulary. The learner needs more vocabularies in learning English Language. They need them to understand what they are going to read, what people are talking about and be able to express/convey their feelings in this language.

Participant 2 with codes 001, 002, 003, 004 learned English Language through mother's assistant, watching of television, reading of English materials and expanding of vocabulary she stated "*Migkataw ako sa English Language kasi si ina na pabagilayn ako nin sa Cartoon an English tapos mga pematian a English ibagidza ko ngin i mana na meaning i niyay bali pedtalo nin sa laki bali paka*"

create ako sa laki a sarili a isip”. My mother makes me to watch English cartoon movies in television and makes me to read English reading materials and I used to ask the meaning of every unfamiliar English language word to my mother. This participant learned English Language in a different way through the initiatives of her mother by letting her to watch an English program in television, read English materials and expanding of vocabulary.

Father assistant to learn English. A father can assist also the learner in learning English language in the absence of mother, but he needs also an enough knowledge to make her/his child learn in this language. Participant 3 coded with 005 learned English

Language with the help of her father. She stated “*Migkataw ako sa English kasi bamandon ako ni abie*”. I learned English Language because my father taught me in this language. This means that the learner’s source of learning at home is only from her father.

Parent’s assistant to learn English. Both parents can assist the learner in learning English language. The learner assisted by both parents the better. Participant 4 coded with 006, 002, 004 stated “*Bamandon ako na ama ko endo ina ama ko amay ka bagilay ako sa tv na aden diko gatuntayan na ibagidza ko*”. My father and my mother they are both teaching me in English Language and when I’m watching television, and I encountered unfamiliar words I ask them on their meaning. Participant 5 with code 006 added that she also learn English language with parent’s assistant. She said “*Bamandon ako nila umie silan kani abie*”. My mother and my father are teaching me English Language.

The student’s study in a variety of ways at home. They must live with family members or other individuals who speak and understand English. For them to learn more, they need to be exposed to this language more through television, books written in English, and other relevant programs.

Families have a significant impact on their children's success in school and throughout life, according to consistent, uplifting, and convincing research. Children typically do better academically, remain in school longer, and enjoy learning more when schools, families, and community organizations collaborate to encourage learning. No matter their origin or financial situation, students with participating parents were found to be more likely to receive higher grades and test scores. They can graduate from high school and continue their education at the postsecondary level, enroll in higher-level programs and be promoted, pass their classes and receive credits, attend school frequently, have better social skills, demonstrate improved behavior, and adjust well to school (Henderson & Mapp, 2022).

Learners Learn English Language in the School

The formulated meanings, codes and themes of the significant statements about English Language learning in the school is shown in table 1.2.

Table 1.2. *English Language Learning in the School*

<i>Participant</i>	<i>Significant Statement</i>	<i>Formulated Meaning</i>	<i>Emergent Theme</i>	<i>Code</i>
1	I’m trying my best to understand the explanation of my teachers.	The learner learns English language with her own understanding/efforts.	Learner’s efforts in understanding the lesson	100
2	My Teacher (Adviser) sometimes she is using Filipino language in explaining our lessons and sometimes English Language.	The teacher uses two languages in explaining the lessons, English and Filipino	Teacher’s translation method	101
3	I’m listening with my teacher.	The learner learns through listening.	Listening to the teacher	102
4	I’m listening with the explanation of my teacher and asking her for everything I do not know in her explanations.	The learner learns through listening and asking of questions with the teacher.	Listening to the teacher Learned through asking questions	102 103
5	Our teacher taught us English Language.	The learners learn English Language because of the teacher’s teachings.	Teacher’s teaching	104

Table 1.2 Presents English Language learning in the school. The participants have different answers on how they learn English language in the school. The result of their learning was affected by different factors existing in the school.

Learner’s efforts in understanding the lesson. The learner can learn English Language by his/her own ways and efforts. It’s up to him/her how he/she learns this language. Participant 1 coded with 100 learns with her own efforts. She said “*Peduntayan ko i ibamando na maestra ko*”. I’m trying my best to understand the explanation of my teachers. The participant 1 her own efforts pushed her into learning in English language by trying her best to understand their lesson explained by their teacher.

Teacher’s translation method. More learners learn by translation from their mother tongue into English. This method is very effective in the beginner or lower grades to understand the lessons. Participant 2 coded 101 mentioned “*Migkataw ako sa English sabap sa explanation a teacher nami sa lessons*”. I learned English Language from the explanation of my teacher in our lessons. Participants 2

learned English language through translation method.

Listening to the teacher. Everyone can learn through listening because it's gives you the moment to understand what someone is trying to express and there's a lot of learners learned English Language through this listening.

Participant 3 coded with 102 learned through listening. She said "*Migkataw ako sa English kasi bakikineg ako sa teacher*". I learned English language because I'm listening with the explanation of my teacher. Participant 4 with 102 codes also learned English Language through listening he stated "*Bakikineg ako teacher amay ka aden diko gatuntayan na bagidza ko sa teacher*". I'm listening to the explanation of my teacher and asking her for everything I do not know in her explanations.

Learned through asking questions. It is a normal way of learning to ask everything unknown matter to the teacher's explanation inside the classroom. Learner may take this opportunity to understand the lessons because it's the responsibility of the teacher to make the lessons clear and understood by the learners. Participant 4 coded 103 affirmed that he also learned through asking questions he said "*Bakikineg ako teacher amay ka aden diko gatuntayan na bagidza ko sa teacher*". I'm listening to the explanation of my teacher and asking her for everything I do not know in her explanations.

Teacher's teaching. The learners always rely on the teacher's teaching in the classroom. The more the teachers use English Language in explaining the lessons the more the learners learn because they are experiencing to listen in English Language with their teacher's who's everyone can be involved or join and interact using English Language too. Participant 5 coded 104 learned English

Language through teacher's teaching and she stated "*Bamanduwan kami ni maam*". Our teacher taught us English Language. The learners may learn English Language in the school through their own initiatives and efforts with the efforts of the teachers in the school. Each learner has its unique ways on how he/she learns English Language and it should be boosted by the positive motivations for the growth of their learning in English Language in the school.

Motivation plays a role in learning a foreign language. If students are intrinsically motivated to learn or speak a language, they will work hard to master it. Extrinsic motivation is when someone is motivated to learn a language for a specific reason, such as to ace a test or advance in their career. The anticipation of some kind of reward is always a powerful motivator and is crucial to the learning of a foreign language.

The process of learning a second or foreign language involves reading up on and learning the language's grammar. Immersion and exposure to "real life" situations are the keys to "learning" a language. The best way to learn a second language, according to expert Stephen Krashen, is to utilize it in everyday situations; if that is not possible, exercises and other techniques can be used. Continuous exposure to the language is necessary to learn a second or foreign language. Like a small kid learning to speak, the learner should ideally be surrounded by native speakers and forced to utilize what she has learned to communicate.

The proper method cannot be used by language learners who do not interact with native speakers. Language learning has been distilled down to its essentials in book method-based courses so that students can navigate a place where that language is the only one spoken. It's best to pick a strategy that you find simple to understand because doing so enhances the likelihood that you'll remember what you learn. Similarly, learning a second language is influenced by intelligence, memory, sex, attitudes, and learning styles. Because of this, a foreign language instructor needs to be conversant with learners' actual circumstances (Thapa, 2021).

The Learners Learn English Language in the Community

The formulated meanings, codes and themes of the significant statements about English Language learning in the community is shown in table 1.3.

Table 1.3 Presents English Language learning in the community. The participants have different responses on how they learn English language in the community. They get learning from the people who are often surround them in the community. Some of them learned English from their playmates, friends, aunt, and cousins.

Learn English with playmates. Participant 1 coded 200 learned English language in the community through her playmates. Usually, some children don't feel shy in her/his playmates in many aspects and they are free to talk its other using any language, teaching its other on anything they want to learn while they are playing. Participant 1 said "*Kaped a nan minsan pedzugay kami sa mga pakat ko o di kayay mga ali ko tapos penggamiten name I English Language*". Sometimes when we are playing together with my friends or my sisters/brothers we are using English Language in our conversation.

Learned English with the help of cousins. In the case of participant 2 coded 201 she learned English language with the help of her cousins. She stated "*Kasi bangingiza ko sa mga mana na English sa mga insan ko*". I always consulting my cousins for every.

English words which are unfamiliar to me. This means that participant 2 always surrounded by their cousins that became a source of her learning in English Language in the community.

Learned English with the help of aunt. Some learners learn with the help of some immediate relatives of their family in the community like what was happened in the case of participant 3 coded 202 according to her "*Bamanduwan ako na babu ko sa kapedtalo sa English*". My aunt is teaching me on how to speak English Language. This showed that they are living in same community or place

that her aunt could teach her in English language.

Table 1.3. English Language Learning in the Community

<i>Participant</i>	<i>Significant Statement</i>	<i>Formulated Meaning</i>	<i>Emergent Theme</i>	<i>Code</i>
1	Sometimes when we are playing together with friends or siblings, we are using English Language conversation.	The learner sometimes using English Language during their playing time.	Learn English with playmates	200
2	I learned English Language with the help of my cousins.	The learner learns English Language with help of cousins.	Learned English with the help of cousins	201
3	My aunt is teaching me on how to speak English Language.	The learner learns English Language with the help of aunt.	Learned English with the help of aunt	202
4	Sometimes we are using English Language in our conversation together with my friends.	The learner using sometimes English Language with friends.	Learned English with friends	203
5	Sometimes My aunts and my friends are teaching me on how to speak English language.	The Aunt's and friends' learner teach her in speaking of English Language.	Learned English with the help of aunt. Learned English with the help of friends	202 203

Learned English with friends. In the case of participant 4 coded 203 the source of her learning in the community was his friends. This means that he and his friends are living in the same community, and they sometimes use English Language during their conversation. According to him “Amengka kuwana, pedzumpata kami sa English sa mga tagapera”. Sometimes we are talking each other using English Language in our conversation together with my friends.

Learned English with the help of aunt and with the help of friends. The participant 5 coded with 202 and 203 has more ways of learning in the community among the participants. She learned English Language both from her friends and her aunt. If we compare her answers to the rest answers of participants, she might learn fast among them because her sources of learning were from her friends and aunt. On the interview when she asked on how did she learn English language in the community, she answered “Minsan bamanduwan ako na mga babu ko apeg mga pakat ko”. Sometimes my aunts and my friends are teaching me on how to speak English language.

The learner may learn English Language from the community if its people know this language especially when they have enough formal education in the school. They only need to use this language in their daily conversation and teach the learner too gradually in using of this language.

Numerous sociocultural systems that generate opportunity and significance for individual members have been amply proven through investigations of learning communities that support real, practical labor (Hutchins, 1996; Cole & Scribner, 1974; Mishler, 1999; Singleton, 2000). Studies of neighborhood and at-home children have demonstrated the close connection between social interaction and learning (Greenfield, 1999; Cole, 1996; Heath, 1983; Scribner, 1990; Rogoff, 1995).

According to Bruner (1973), Cole (1988), Lave (1988), Mehan (1983), Norman (1980), Rogoff (1994), and Wertsch (1997), learning theory has changed from a cognitive theory of acquisition to a social theory of involvement. A systems or network perspective on the activity is adopted by a social view of learning. According to Dewey (1916) and Vygotsky (1978), the process of developing one's intellect involves negotiating meaning with others in the context of daily life. Instead of accumulating static knowledge, learning happens through actual experiences that include actively manipulating and experimenting with ideas (Bruner, 1973; Cole, 1998; Dewey, 1916).

Barriers in English Language Learning

The barriers in English Language learning by the learners at home, school and community are presented in tables 2.1, 2.2, and 2.3.

Barriers of English Language at Home

The formulated meanings, codes and themes of the significant statements about barriers of English Language at home is shown in table 2.1.

Table 2.1 Presents Barriers of English Language learning at home. The participants of this study have different answers on this matter. Some of them encountered the barriers of learning in English Language at home but the others of them have no barriers in learning of this language.

Embarrassment from the family member. The participant 1 whose emergent theme has a code of 300 said “Minsan na ipeg correction ako na mga lukes ko ka pegkamali ako tapos pakaya bun”. Sometimes my family correcting me in speaking English Language, and I feel a shame. Her answer showed that her barriers in English Language learning at home is shyness for committing mistakes in speaking

English language.

Mockings from the cousins with the error committed. Participant 2 with the code 301 feels shy when mocked by her cousins. The corrections made by their family and the unpleasant reactions of some close relatives against English language like mock and laughing bother her to use this language. During the interview she said “*Kasi amengka galimban ako na pedtatawan ako na mga insan ko angayangay gayan ako*”. I feel shame every time I make a mistake in speaking English because my cousins laugh at me.

Table 2.1. *Barriers of English Language Learning at Home*

Participant	Significant Statement	Formulated Meaning	Emergent Theme	Code
1	Sometimes my family correcting me in speaking English Language and I feel a shame.	The participant's embarrassment from that family members that hinders learned English through the corrections.	Embarrassment from the family member	300
2	I feel shame every time I make a mistake in Speaking English because my cousins laugh at me.	Learner feels shy when mocked by her cousins when she committed errors in speaking English.	Mockings from the cousins with the error committed.	301
3	My parents are not educated so they are not able to speak English Language.	The learner's parents are uneducated.	Lack of parents' formal education.	302
4	Nothing because my parents are both educated and they are able to speak English Language.	The learner's family is educated that's why there are no barriers in learning English at home.	No barriers in English Language at home	303
5	Nothing because my parents are both educated and they are able to speak English Language.	The learner's family is educated that's why there are no barriers in learning English at home.	No barriers in English Language at home	303

Lack of parents' formal education. Other factors of the barriers in English language learning at home is lack of parents' formal education. Like in the case of participant 3 with the code of 302 and this is the extreme cause why this participant could not be able to learn English Language at home according to her “*Mga lukes ko na di mataw edtalo sa English*”. My parents are not educated so they are not able to speak English Language.

No barriers in English Language at home. In the case of participant 4 and 5 whose emergent theme has a code of both 303 they did not encountered barriers in English Language learning at home because their parents are educated, and they are able to speak English Language. Participant 4 said “*Da bun kasi si ina si ama mataw sa English Language*”. Nothing because my parents are both educated, and they can speak English Language. Participant 5 also stated “*Da bun kasi si abie si umie mataw edtalo sa English Language*”. Nothing because my parents are both educated, and they can speak English Language.

Learners at home should not be given in negative comments when they are trying to speak English and people who always interact with them at home must teach them and find a positive way on how to make a correction on their own mistakes in English Language.

Mother tongue interference is another factor that has an impact on language development. One's mother tongue is sometimes referred to as their parent's language. "Mother tongue," 2015. Mother-tongue interference is the term used to describe how the learner's native language affects how quickly they pick up the target language. The language that the learner hopes to acquire (L2) is the target language (2015, "Contrasting Analysis").

Learning a foreign language can be challenging since some aspects of the pronunciation, grammar, and structures can vary from their native speech. Beginning learners of a foreign language struggle to communicate effectively due to interference from their mother tongues. And over time, they can learn a foreign language, though at varying rates depending on their varying levels of intelligence.

Barriers of English Language in the school

The formulated meanings, codes and themes of the significant statements about barriers of English Language in the school is shown in table 2.2

Table 2.2 Presents Barriers of English Language learning in school. The school comprises of different learners with different characteristics. Some of them with a good character and some are with negative characters. These kinds of learners affect the growth/development of learning in English Language in school.

No barriers of learning English in school. Participant 1 coded with 400 has no barriers in learning English in school because they are not prohibited for using English Language in school, they can use this language at any time they want. She stated, “*Da bun, gapakayan bun a pedtalo sa English Language siya sa classroom apya ngin a oras*”. Nothing because in the school we can use English Language

at any time we want. It means that it's up to them how they are interested to learn and use English Language in school.

Table 2.2. *Barriers of English Language Learning in School*

Participant	Significant Statement	Formulated Meaning	Emergent Theme	Code
1	Nothing because we can use English Language at any time we want.	The learner can use English Language at any time she wants.	No barriers of learning English in school.	400
2	We are seldom using English Language because the rest in the class don't understand this language.	Majority of the learners in the class don't understand English language	The seldom used of English in the classroom	401
3	I feel shy if I'm trying to speak English because the rest of my classmates are mocking me.	The learner feels shy in using English Language with her classmates because of the negative comments of the classmates.	Mocking of the classmates	402
4	My classmates are laughing with me when I'm asking or when I'm reading and I didn't articulate correctly some words of English Language that I'm trying to express and read.	The learner feels shy with the classmates in using English Language because of the negative comments of the classmates.	Mocking of the classmates	402
5	My classmates are laughing with me when I'm asking or when I'm reading and I didn't articulate correctly some words of English Language that I'm trying to express and read.	The learner feels shy with the classmates in using English Language because of the negative comments of the classmates.	Mocking of the classmates	402

The seldom used of English in the classroom. This is the second barrier encountered by the participants of this study in school. The irregularity of using English Language inside the classroom or in the school because majority of the learners do not understand the language. They can't express their feelings/opinions in English Language and so the participants don't have the opportunity to fully exercise and practice this language which cause them lack of exercises in this language. Participant 2 whose emergent theme has a code of 401 said "...*minsan bu kapedtalo nami sa English kasi kena langon mataw edtalo sa English*". We are seldom use English Language because the rest in the class don't understand this language.

Mocking of the classmates. Participants 3, 4, and 5 have codes of 402 agreed that their barrier in English Language learning in school is shy with their classmates because of their negative reactions when they committed mistakes for using in English Language. Participant 3 statement "*Gayan ako pedtalo sa English ka pedhuri i ped*". I feel shy if I'm trying to speak English because the rest of my classmates are mocking with me. Participant 4 statement in support to the response of participant 3 "*Mga classmate ko bamedtatawa amengka kuwana pembatia ta sa English Language or bagidsa ta sa English Language bali pedtatawa silan langon amengka di ta ged gabales bali gayan ako*". My classmates are laughing with me when I'm asking or when I'm reading, and I didn't correctly articulate some words of English Language that I'm trying to express and read. Participant 5 statement also showed the similarity in the response of participant 3 and 4 she said "*Amay ka bagidza ta sa English Language tapos di taged gabales na pedhuri I mga classmate ko*". My classmates are laughing with me when I'm asking or and I didn't correctly articulate some words of English Language that I'm trying to express.

The participants of this study were affected by different phenomenon existed within the school. All the barriers they have should be addressed in a very positive ways by their teacher and their selves too. Everyone should make an adjustment towards English Language learning in the school.

The fault lies with the educational system because teachers should be teaching students how to utilize the language they are learning, not only how to "prepare" them for exams (Subramanian, 1985). As a result, students work hard to achieve the required grade and lack internal motivation to study English for other objectives, progressing to higher grades with inconsistent or even insufficient English proficiency.

Khaniya (1990, cited in Ghorbani, 2009) claims that "a large number of teachers help students cope with examinations in order to preserve their reputation as good teachers" (p. 51). Teachers may only teach English for testing purposes out of dread for their pupils' performance on public exams and the guilt, shame, or embarrassment that comes with it (Alderson & Wall, 1993). Different requirements apply to what teachers should do in the classroom, including the use of communicative resources and the provision of communicative places. Speaking ability is the most undervalued of the four language abilities in foreign language training, which is unfortunate given that most teachers do not give them equal weight.

Since speaking the language fluently is the first step in mastering a language, introverted persons may find it challenging to learn how to communicate in a foreign language. Students that are more adept at communicating don't mind taking chances or making errors as long as their messages are understood by their audience. Because it seems strange to them, shy pupils tend to avoid communicating in a foreign language. As a result of their limited exposure, language learning is substantially slower.

Barriers of English Language in the Community

The formulated meanings, codes, and themes of the significant statements about barriers of English Language in the community is shown in table 2.3.

Table 2.3. *Barriers of English Language learning in the Community*

Participant	Significant Statement	Formulated Meaning	Emergent Theme	Code
1	Some members of the community and mocking me when they hear I'm speaking English Language. They say/act/show something against me in a lower voice.	Unpleasant reactions of the community bother the learner for using of English Language.	Mocking from the community	500
2	The community does not know/speak English Language.	The learner doesn't learn English Language from the community because they are not using English Language.	English is not used in the community	501
3	Most of the people in the community doesn't know/speak English Language.	The learner learns less English Language from the community because the majority are not using English Language.	English is not used in the community	501
4	Our neighbors don't know/speak English Language.	The learner doesn't learn English Language from the community because they are not using English Language.	English is not used in the community	501
5	I can't speak English Language because the people in the community don't know/speak English Language.	The learner doesn't learn English Language from the community because they are not using English Language.	English is not used in the community	501

Table 2.3 Presents Barriers of English Language learning in the community. In terms of community barriers in English Language learning the participants have only two barriers. Mocking from the community and English is not used in the community.

Mocking from the community. The participant 1 with the code of 500 said that the cause bothered her in speaking/using of English language in their community is that the people in community where they are living has negative reactions for someone speaks English Language, they seems like they hear stranger speaking in front of them and make undesirable reactions against that person and this was proven by participant 1 with the code of 500 as she stated "*Kaper, pedtalo silan sa pedzuri mana pabrinig uway na pedo*". Some members of the community mocking with me when they hear.

I'm speaking of English Language. They say/act/show something against me in a lower voice.

English is not used in the community. The participants 2, 3, 4, & 5 coded as 501, the learners met barriers in learning English Language in the community because English Language is not used in the community. It is supported by the participants when they mentioned that in the community no one is speaking English and the people living in the community don't speak English. Participant 2 statement "*So mga taw sa community na di pedtalo sa English*". The community doesn't know/speak English Language. Participant 3 statement regarding this matter "*Kagina kaper/kadakelan kano mga taw sa community na dimataw edtalo sa English*". The majority people in the society doesn't know/speak English Language. Participant 4 statement as support to their responses "*Mga pagubay nami na di mataw edtalo sa English*". Our neighbors don't know/speak English Language. Participant 5 response is also another support statement on their responses for not using of English Language in their community and she said "*Minsan di ta ged pakadtalo sa English Language ka di ged mataw i kaped a taw lo*". Sometimes I can't speak English Language because some people in the community don't know/speak English Language.

As shown in the majority responses of the participants their community is not using English Language. The learners did not learn from their community in regards with English Language. They need to thoroughly help their selves to learn English Language by their own efforts.

Immersion and exposure to "real life" situations are the keys to "learning" a language. The best way to learn a second language, according to expert Stephen Krashen, is to utilize it in everyday situations; if that is not possible, exercises and other techniques can be used. Constant exposure is necessary to learn a second or foreign language. Like a small kid learning to speak, the learner should ideally be surrounded by native speakers and forced to utilize what she has learned to communicate.

The proper method cannot be used by language learners who do not interact with native speakers. Language learning has been distilled down to its essentials in book method-based courses so that students can navigate a place where that language is the only one spoken. Picking an approach that is simple for you will improve your ability to remember what you have learned. Similarly, learning a second language is influenced by intelligence, memory, sex, attitudes, and learning styles. Because of this, a foreign language instructor needs

to be conversant with learners' actual circumstances.

Theory Generated from the Study

This study generated Guiaria Kayog is theory 2023. It is a theory of English Language learning at home, school and in community. The researcher professed that in order to develop the learners of Bangsamoro in learning English Language the teachers, parents, community and learners should engage in using English language. In this way, the learners can easily learn English Language if they engage with people around them who are using English Language. The researcher also believed that a great exposure with a lot of practices of using English language will lead them to better ability to use English Language.

As a result, the researcher affirms that through the use of English Language with the help of teachers, parents, community can help improve the Bangsamoro learners in learning English Language.

Conclusion

Language acquisition among Bangsamoro learners encompasses a multifaceted process influenced by several key factors. Exposure to the English language, whether through television, radio, internet, or formal instruction in schools, serves as a foundational element in fostering language acquisition. Furthermore, interaction with English-speaking individuals, be it teachers, peers, or family members, facilitates the internalization of language patterns and vocabulary, while motivation acts as a driving force propelling learners towards English proficiency, whether for academic, career, or social reasons.

Each learner employs unique strategies, ranging from vocabulary memorization to active participation in language activities, to enhance their language skills. Supportive environments, characterized by encouragement from parents, teachers, and peers, as well as exposure to English-rich settings like clubs or extracurricular activities, further bolster language acquisition efforts. These combined factors underscore the intricate journey towards acquiring English proficiency among Bangsamoro learners and illuminate the significance of addressing barriers to facilitate effective language learning experiences.

Based on the summary of findings, it is concluded that the English language learning experiences of Bangsamoro learners are hindered by limited opportunities to practice the language at home, in school, and within the community. This lack of exposure is compounded by feelings of embarrassment, mockery, and the influence of parents' educational backgrounds.

Furthermore, it is concluded that students primarily acquire English language skills through their own efforts, supplemented by support from teachers, parents, relatives, playmates, and friends. These findings underscore the importance of addressing barriers to English language learning and fostering supportive environments to facilitate language acquisition among Bangsamoro learners.

Based on the findings and conclusions of the study the following are recommended. English Language should be used frequently by the learners at home, school, and in the community. Learners may consider mingling with English language users to improve their English Learning. Learners should have more vocabularies and learn the correct usage of English Language to be more confident.

Parents and other members of the family should support the English learning of their children and relatives. Parents may use gadgets as source of learning in English Language learning for the learners in home like watching of English programs in the TV, YouTube and others.

Teachers should always make all kinds of strategies to motivate learners in the use of English Language inside the classroom. Teachers should use English Language in explaining all English subjects. Teachers should make a daily activity for reading in English reading materials.

The community should show positive reactions in speaking of English Language. The community should have an enough level of education to help their children in the English Language learning.

Future researchers investigating the English language learning experiences of Bangsamoro learners can utilize this study as a foundational reference. By examining the unique context of Bangsamoro learners at Mapayag Elementary School, this study provides insights into the acquisition of English language skills within a rural community setting. The findings elucidate the challenges faced by Bangsamoro learners, including limited opportunities for language practice and the influence of familial and societal factors on language acquisition. Moreover, the study highlights the strategies employed by learners and the supportive environments necessary for effective language learning. Future researchers can build upon these findings to explore additional factors impacting language acquisition among Bangsamoro learners and to develop tailored interventions aimed at enhancing English proficiency within this specific demographic.

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